

GUANYLALKYLUREAS AND THEIR METALLIC COMPLEXES. PART VII. GUANYL $\textit{cyclo}$ HEXYLUREA

By R. L. DUTTA AND SUBRATA LAHIRY

Guanylcyclohexylurea and its complexes with copper(II), nickel(II), and palladium(II) have been prepared and their properties studied. The complexes are all of the *bis*-guanylurea type and have the usual colour: copper (rose-red), nickel (yellow to orange), and palladium (pale cream). The copper complex is paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.87$ B.M.) whereas the nickel and palladium complexes are diamagnetic. The rose-red copper complex ($\lambda_{\text{max}} 530\text{-}540$ m μ) changes in solution at pH 4 to the blue-coloured *monoguanylurea* complex ($\lambda_{\text{max}} 660$ m μ). It has not been possible, however, to isolate the blue-coloured complex in the pure state.

It has recently been observed in this laboratory that dicyandiamide and an alcohol react in presence of copper salts to form the complex copper salt of the guanylurea with an alkyl substituent, corresponding to that of the alcohol used, at the urea end of the molecule. From the rose-coloured complex the guanylalkylurea was obtained after decomposing with H₂S. Thus several guanylalkylureas, namely, guanyl-methyl-, -ethyl-, -butylⁿ-, -butyl^l-, -amyl^l-, hexylⁿ-urea sulphates were isolated (Dutta and Rây, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 499). A comprehensive study of the copper (II), nickel (II), palladium (II), and cobalt (III) complexes of these ligands has also been made (Dutta *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, 36, 567, 576; 1960, 37, 573; Dutta, *ibid.*, 1960, 37, 499).

It has now been found that dicyandiamide and *cyclohexanol* react in a similar manner in presence of copper acetate to form the red-violet complex, copper-*bis*-guanylcyclohexylurea acetate.

From the complex copper sulphate, the reagent *guanylcyclohexylurea* sulphate was isolated as colorless crystals, and the nature of the copper (II), nickel (II), and palladium (II) complexes was studied.

Copper (II) gives rise to the usual rose-red anhydro-base in alkaline medium. This is stable towards boiling in aqueous ethanol medium. In addition, several salts of the base, namely, sulphate, chloride, iodide, perchlorate, and acetate, have also been characterised, which are insoluble in water, but as observed with the other substituted *guanylalkylureas* (*loc. cit.*), most of these complexes (sulphate salt is an exception) are soluble in ethanol. The complexes are paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.87$ B.M.). An ethanolic solution of the chloride salt shows an absorption maximum at 530-540 $m\mu$. At a pH of about 4, the red-violet colour changes to a blue one ($\lambda_{\text{max}} 660 m\mu$), which is indicative of the existence of a copper-*monoguanlylcyclohexylurea* complex (cf. Dutta, *loc. cit.*). Like the blue complex copper-*mono-guanylmethyl-* and copper-*mono-guanylethylurea* chlorides (Dutta *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, p. 567), it has not been possible to isolate a similar complex in the case of this ligand.

Nickel (II) forms in alkaline medium a yellow anhydro-base. Besides the base, the complex nickel sulphate, chloride, bromide, and iodide have also been isolated. The complexes are diamagnetic, indicating a planar structure, characteristic of penetration complexes of nickel with dsp^2 bonds. The ethanol solution of the chloride salt shows an absorption maximum at 440-450 $m\mu$.

Palladium (II) also forms a pale cream-coloured anhydro-base. The complex sulphate has also been described. Like nickel (II) complexes, palladium (II) complexes are also diamagnetic.

EXPERIMENTAL

Guanylcyclohexylurea Sulphate

Dicyandiamide (5 g.), copper acetate (5 g.), and *cyclohexanol* (50 c.c.) were heated under reflux on a water bath. The reaction was slow; the characteristic violet colour developed after a few hours. When the reaction mixture became deep violet in colour, it was filtered and the filtrate allowed to stand a day or two in the open with occasional scratching. When fine crystals began to separate, the mixture was left in the frigidaire for a few more days, when the complex copper-*guanylcyclohexylurea* acetate crystallised out in quantity. The crystals were filtered, dissolved in hot ethanol (50 c.c.) and treated with an aqueous solution of ammonium sulphate, when the complex copper sulphate was precipitated. The dried complex sulphate was then powdered, suspended in water (10-15 c.c.) and decomposed with H_2S . After removing the CuS , the filtrate was freed of H_2S by air, cooled in ice bath and treated with a large volume of acetone, when colorless crystals of *guanylcyclohexylurea* sulphate separated out. These were then filtered and dried over $CaCl_2$. The substance is highly soluble in water. This responds to all the usual tests of *guanylurea*. (Found: N, 24.45; SO_4 , 20.90. $(C_8H_{16}ON_4)_2 \cdot H_2SO_4$ requires N, 24.03; SO_4 , 20.60%).

Copper-bis-guanylcyclohexylurea Acetate

The preceding crude complex copper acetate was purified by recrystallisation from hot ethanol, and then dried in air. {Found: Cu, 10.83; N, 19.60; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 6.50. $[Cu(C_8H_{16}O_4N_2)](CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires Cu, 10.84; N, 19.11; H_2O , 6.14%}.

Copper-bis-guanylcyclohexylurea Base

An ethanol solution of the complex copper acetate was treated with an NaOH solution (dil.) when the complex copper base separated as a dull rose precipitate. This was purified by recrystallisation from a large volume of boiling ethanol. It is insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in ethanol or acetone. The compound liberates ammonia from ammonium salts and suffers no loss in weight even at 130°. {Found: Cu, 14.88. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_4\text{N})_2]$ requires Cu, 14.78%}.

The *sulphate* was obtained as a rose-red crystalline precipitate, as described earlier. {Found: Cu, 11.52; N, 20.80; SO_4 , 17.30. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_4)_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 11.64; N, 20.53; SO_4 , 17.60%}. The substance is paramagnetic. $\chi_g = 2.092 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m = 1141 \times 10^{-6}$; diamagnetic correction = 273.4×10^{-6} ; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.87$ B.M. (temp. 35°).

The following salts of the complex copper base were obtained as rose-red crystals by metathesis of complex copper acetate and the appropriate alkali metal salts in aqueous ethanolic medium and were further purified from ethanol.

Chloride: {Found: Cu, 11.90; Cl, 13.31; H_2O , 5.20. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_4)_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 11.99; Cl, 13.41; H_2O , 5.10%}.

Iodide: {Found: Cu, 8.82; I, 35.40; H_2O , 5.10. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_4)_2]\text{I}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 8.80; I, 35.19; H_2O , 4.99%}.

Perchlorate: {Found: Cu, 8.82; H_2O , 9.90. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_4)_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 9.04; H_2O , 10.25%}.

Nickel-bis-guanylcyclohexylurea Base

It was prepared by digesting on a water bath a solution of nickel sulphate (1 M) and freshly prepared guanylcyclohexylurea sulphate solution (1.5 M; obtained as described under the reagent) with dilute alkali solution. The precipitated yellow compound was filtered, washed with water, and dried over KOH. This liberates ammonia from ammonium salts. {Found: Ni, 13.60. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_4)_2]$ requires Ni, 13.82%}.

Chloride.—The complex nickel base was suspended in ethanol and triturated with 2N-HCl to a neutral reaction, when a clear, deep orange-red solution was formed. This deposited orange-red crystals on cooling. {Found: Ni, 11.50; Cl, 14.12; H_2O , 2.00. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_4)_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 11.59; Cl, 14.02; H_2O , 1.77%}. The compound is diamagnetic. $\chi_g = -0.36 \times 10^{-6}$ (35°). The following salts were obtained as described under copper.

Bromide: {Found: Ni, 10.25. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_4)_2]\text{Br}_2$ requires Ni, 10.01%}.

Iodide: {Found: Ni, 8.75; I, 37.20. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_4)_2]\text{I}_2$ requires Ni, 8.62; I, 37.30%}.

Sulphate: {Found: Ni, 10.80; SO_4 , 17.85; H_2O , 2.90. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_4)_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 10.85; SO_4 , 17.75; H_2O , 2.90%}.

Palladium-bis-guanylcyclohexylurea Base

It was obtained as a pale cream precipitate by the action of alkali on a mixture of sodium chloropalladite (PdCl_2 , 1 M) and the reagent (1.5 M). {Found: Pd, 22.60; N, 23.54. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_4)_2]$ requires Pd, 22.48; N, 23.59%}.

Sulphate.—The complex palladium base was suspended in ethanol, neutralised with HCl (dil.), filtered, and then treated with aqueous ammonium sulphate. The precipitated complex sulphate was filtered, washed with water and ethanol, and dried in air. (Found : Pd, 18.30; SO₄, 16.20; H₂O, 3.00. [Pd (C₉H₁₀ON₂)₂]SO₄ · H₂O requires Pd, 18.12; SO₄, 16.30; H₂O, 3.05%). The substance is diamagnetic. $\chi_g = -0.33 \times 10^{-6}$ (31°).

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INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE
CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE,
JADAVPUR, CALCUTTA-32.

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